

**Draft Guidance for Trusted Research Environments
(TREs) when assessing Safe People and Safe
Organisations accessing sensitive data**

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Introduction

Across the UK there are many different secure environments providing access to sensitive data for research. There are several names for such environments including Secure Data Environments (SDEs), Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and Safe Havens. We use the term Host Organisations to refer to those which hosts and controls a TRE. Regardless of the name, they generally follow the [Five Safes](#) principles when assessing the “safety” of a research Project. Principles and good practices for assessing the “Safe People” component of the Five Safes framework were developed within the [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#) (Alliance) Paper – “[Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#)”.

Purpose

Safe People is an important aspect of the [Five Safes](#), only researchers that have been validated against appropriate criteria should be able to access data for research. Host Organisations should assess the knowledge, skills, research purpose and incentives of Users and User Organisations who wish to gain access to data for research and check to ensure that they treat any data with the confidentiality and sensitivity necessary. These researchers need to show they have appropriate credentials, training and attachment to legitimate organisations. Here we expand on these principles to provide additional practical guidance for Host Organisations to consider when assessing Safe People (which also considers the safety of the organisation with whom people are affiliated i.e. “Safe Organisations”).

These principles have been gathered using existing good practices and consultations with a variety of groups detailed below. The principles and practical guidance associated are things Host Organisations need to consider when assessing Users and User Organisations who access data for research purposes. These principles have been compiled based on existing UK standards and practices such as the [MRC Data Sharing Policy](#), however, where known and relevant, an international equivalent is noted.

Methodology and Acknowledgements

This document is an output from the Alliance. Contributors to the development of this guidance include:

- Alliance members including members of the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group
- Representatives from the NHS Data for Research and Development Programme and NHS Research Secure Data Environment Network
- Representatives from the UK Trusted Research Environment Community
- Representatives from the HDR UK Public Advisory Board

These guidelines are an output of the Sensitive Data Research Passport and Registry pilot Project, one of the [four pilot Projects funded by DSIT/UKRI](#). This Project also funded the development of a web-based

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platform to support Data Custodians, Users and Organisations to share information and record decisions supporting the assessment of Safe People and Safe Organisations: the Safe Organisation and User Registry for Sensitive Data (SOURSD). SOURSD functionality aligns with this guidance (see complementary technical specification).

Throughout this document, each practical guideline references the relevant numbered principles and best practices from [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#) and we have also noted where there is a relevant clause Alliance standard [Data Access Agreement \(DAA\)](#). In summary:

Terminology

We have aligned our terminology with the definitions in **(DAA)** where relevant. In summary:

- **“Approved Project”**: means projects approved by the Host Organisation, to be undertaken in a TRE/ SDE/ Safe Haven, specifying which Users from which User Organisations can work on the Project. Project approval will assess each aspect of the Five Safes i.e. not just “Safe People”.
- **“Approved Users”** means the individual, who, if approved, will be accessing in a TRE/SDE/Safe Haven for Approved Project(s). Another term could be data “User” (utilised by SOURSD) or individual (equivalent term within [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#)).
- **“Host Organisation”**: means the organisation which hosts and controls the TRE/ SDE / Safe Haven providing access to data for research. The Host Organisation can be the “Data Custodian” (equivalent term within [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#), and utilised by SOURSD).
“User Organisation”: means an organisation (university, research organisation, administrative body or other) which is responsible for individuals using a TRE service in the context of the Approved Project. Another term could be data “Organisation” (equivalent term within [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#) and utilised by SOURSD).
- **“User”**: The individual, prior to approval, who is applying for access and use of the data with the Host Organisation.
- **“User Researcher Affiliation”**: means the process of User Organisations confirming that a User is affiliated with them. An affiliation could be through a contract of employment, an honorary contract or enrolment as a student.
- **“User Researcher Validation”**: means the process of the Host Organisation reviewing Users and User Organisations to assess their “safeness” to access sensitive data. If a User/User Organisation has been assessed as “safe” by a Host Organisation, then they are classified as “validated”. Validating a User or User Organisation to work on a specific Project is distinct from Project Approval (see below) e.g. a User could be considered “safe” and be validated to work on a Project, but the Project is then not approved for other reasons.

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Users

The following data should be provided by Users to be assessed by Host Organisations.

What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
Full legal name	To check a User’s identity i.e. they are who they say they are.	<p>It is recommended that records of the first, last and middle names of Users are maintained.</p> <p>Host Organisations may wish to independently assess individual User. Alternatively, they may wish to defer to the relevant User Organisation to confirm User affiliations once they have passed the relevant identity checks i.e. require the User Organisations to carry out identity checks.</p> <p>For Host Organisations who independently assess User identity, they may wish to consider checking the first, last and middle names of a User against their official government documentation e.g. Passport, Drivers Licence</p>	A1
Other known name(s)	To check a User’s identity i.e. they are who they say they are.	As above	A1
Location	To assess whether a User’s location complies with legal requirements around data access including UK GDPR rules regarding	<p>The location refers to the place where the User is physically located when accessing the data (not their country of residence, nationality etc).</p> <p>Location of a user impacts access to data as those who are located outside the UK will be subject to the rules around international transfers under GDPR.</p>	

¹ [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#)

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
	international transfers of data.	<p>See ICO's guide to international transfers for recommendations for how to assess the impact of a Users location on an Approved Project.</p> <p>Note: Whether or not GDPR is relevant to a project will depend on whether the data is considered personal data or not.</p> <p>Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICO Anonymisation Guidance • ICO Research Provisions 	
<p>For each current employment with an organisation / university affiliation: Affiliated User Organisation name and relationship with User Organisation</p>	<p>To identify any User Organisation affiliations of a User who is intending to access data</p> <p>To establish whether a User is substantively employed by an Organisation, on an honorary contract, a student or another relationship.</p>	<p>Users could potentially have multiple current affiliations e.g. they could have part-time contracts working as an NHS clinician, a university user and a consultant for a Small/ Medium Enterprise (SME).</p> <p>For each Approved Project, the User Organisation has a responsibility to ensure the Approved User adheres to the terms of access for that Project. Therefore, for each Project a User is working on, the relevant User Organisations needs to be captured (see Project section).</p> <p>The Host Organisation may wish to also consider current User affiliations for User Organisations who are NOT working on the Approved Project in question to assess if any potential conflicts of interest could impact a Users “Safeness” to work on the project. For example, the data being accessed for an Approved Project by a User based upon their university affiliated User Organisation might also be of interest for marketing purposes to an SME with which the User has an affiliation.</p>	<p>A2 and A4</p>

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice ¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
		<p>Host Organisations may wish to consider only checking the affiliation of a User with a Host Organisation once, i.e. affiliation confirmation is not required on a per Project basis. This is to aid in streamlining processes. However, Host Organisations should consider providing a mechanism for User Organisations to easily see the Projects a User is validated to work on, and if necessary, request that a User is either added or removed from a Project.</p> <p>NB. Confirmation of affiliation for each User is provided by the User Organisation (see User Organisation).</p>	
<p>Professional email address of the User for each current User Organisation affiliation</p>	<p>To assess whether a User is employed by / a student with the relevant User Organisation</p>	<p>We recommend that Host Organisations check that the email address is valid and is directed to the relevant User Organisation domain e.g. by checking the domain corresponds to the User Organisation (the address after the “@” in an email address) and sending an email to the address and requiring that the User replies appropriately.</p>	<p>A1, A2 and A4</p>
<p>Professional registration name and ID</p>	<p>To assess whether a User has the necessary accreditation and/or expertise to work with the data effectively</p>	<p>Users accessing Digital Economy Act (DEA) accredited environments are required to hold the professional registration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Statistics Authority (UKSA) Accredited Researcher (AR) <p>Non-DEA accredited environments may also wish to consider this professional registration as a requirement as the training is tailored to Users</p>	<p>A2, A3 Clause 1 of the Alliance DAA</p>

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
		<p>working on sensitive data within secure environments.</p> <p>Other professional registrations may be relevant e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Medical Council (GMC) • Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) • Health and Care Allied Professional Council (HCPC) 	
<p>Safe Researcher Training (SRT) certificate or equivalent (with expiry dates)</p>	<p>To assess whether a User has undertaken and/or renewed relevant Information Governance training</p>	<p>Maintaining records of training courses, certificates and associated expiry dates for each User is recommended. Consider reminding Users to renew their training as relevant expiry dates approach. Consider removing access to data for an Approved Project if a Users training has lapsed.</p> <p>Potential safe researcher training courses to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ONS safe researcher training course – delivered by ONS, SCADR, UKDS (required for researchers accessing DEA accredited environments) • The Medical Research Council, regulatory support centre – Research, GDPR and confidentiality quiz • Any mandatory Host Organisation specific training courses 	<p>A3</p>
<p>Signed User declaration</p>	<p>To ensure that the User understands and agrees to adhere to the terms of access when</p>	<p>Host Organisations may require a user declaration, and if so, it is recommended that the Terms of Use present as ‘click through’ terms that the Approved User must accept before accessing the TRE.</p>	<p>A4, A7, Annex 1 to the Alliance DAA</p>

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
	accessing sensitive data within a secure environment	Template terms are available in the Annex 1 of the Alliance DAA.	
Experience	To ensure that the User has the relevant experience to analyse data as assessed by their employment history, qualifications, publication records	<p>Host Organisations may wish to independently assess individual User experience, or alternatively they may wish to defer to the relevant User Organisation to only confirm affiliations of their Users they believe have appropriate experience.</p> <p>For independent assessment, this information could be obtained from a copy of an up-to-date User CV or from analysis of a related public ORCID profile (for Users who have set up such an account and where the data is up to date and accurate).</p> <p>Host Organisations may wish to cross check information within a Users CV/ORCID with other professional information online e.g. LinkedIn profiles or profiles on User Organisation webpages.</p> <p>User experience may not be assessed in isolation e.g. the collective experience of the team of Users working on an Approved project may be considered. For example, a highly experienced Project lead investigator could oversee the work of less experienced PhD students. If only PhD students were accessing the data without a supervisor, then the experience of the Users may become more of a consideration for Host Organisations.</p>	A2
Experience: Previous work on sensitive		Host Organisations may wish to independently assess individual User experience working on previous project, or alternatively they may wish to defer to the relevant User Organisation to only confirm affiliations	

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice ¹ (summarised in Appendix A)
data projects.		<p>of their Users they believe have appropriate experience.</p> <p>This information could be implied through assessment of User publications / projects (as obtained from Experience - row above) or it could be obtained through Host Organisations sharing Project metadata with each other (including which Users and User Organisations have worked on the Project). It is recommended that Project metadata is shared utilising the Data Use Register (DUR) standard.</p>	
Project Identifier and details.	To assess a User’s “Safeness” in the context of the specific Project.	<p>A User’s “Safeness” could potentially change given the wider context of a project. Therefore, Host Organisations may wish to assess a User in the context of a Project (see below Projects section).</p> <p>For each Project the User Organisation who is responsible for the User on the Project should be captured and the User assessed in the context of the Safeness of the User Organisation (see User Organisation section).</p> <p>The sponsor of a project may also be a consideration. Users may have to be approved to work on a project by a Sponsor instead of / in addition to their User Organisation e.g. this may be a requirement for health data projects in England where this is a requirement from the Health Research Authority (HRA).</p>	

User Organisation

The following data should be provided by User Organisations to be assessed by Host Organisations.

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how)	Relevant Best Practice² (summarised in Appendix A)
User Organisation legal name, address, sector and other details	To check the identity of User Organisations	<p>The legal name and address should be for the User Organisation who is approving (employment contract or student enrolment) their Users.</p> <p>Large companies may have many different subsidiaries. If it is the subsidiary who is the legal entity employing the User accessing data for a specific Project, then it should be the subsidiary who should be recorded as the registered User Organisation. Potentially this could mean that many different subsidiaries of large companies are registered as separate User Organisations.</p> <p>If an international company is a User Organisation (i.e. employing Users working on Projects) then Host Organisations may wish to consider also capturing their UK subsidiaries, as part of their assessment that there is relevant expertise within the User Organisation overall of UK law etc.</p> <p>For UK based subsidiaries, Host Organisations may also wish to also consider recording and assessing their parent international company.</p>	A1

² [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#)

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<p>Companies House ID for UK based User Organisations (or other regulatory sources – for non UK User Organisations)</p>	<p>To check the identity and properties of User Organisations</p>	<p>For any UK based User Organisations, Host Organisations should consider checking their records against those listed on Companies House (or other regulatory sources – for non-UK User Organisations).</p> <p>Host Organisations may wish to check the properties of the company as listed within Companies House against their access criteria e.g. a Host Organisation may only wish to work with public sector organisations.</p>	<p>A1 and A4</p>
<p>Charity registration identifier – Charity Commission (England and Wales) OSCR – Scottish Charity Register Charity Commission for NI</p>	<p>To check the charity status of the User Organisation.</p> <p>Host Organisations may view applications from the charity sector differently. There may also be a cost implication for each Approved Project.</p>	<p>Host Organisations may wish to verify the details provided match those listed on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Charity Registration ID for England and NI • The Scottish Charity Regulator (OSCR) for Scotland • The Charity Commission for Northern Ireland 	<p>A2</p>
<p>Persistent digital identifier – Research Organisation Registry</p>	<p>To check the identity of User Organisations</p>	<p>It is recommended to search and maintain records of a User Organisation’s ROR ID. Host Organisations may wish to check that the properties of the User Organisation captured within their ROR align with those provided by the User Organisation.</p> <p>ROR identifiers can also be used to support transparency of Approved Projects within DURs, helping to make Projects FAIR.</p>	<p>A1</p>

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<p>Organisation website (and if relevant subsidiary website)</p>	<p>To check the identity of User Organisations and as part of due diligence checks</p>	<p>Assessment of the information on the User Organisation from their website information.</p> <p>Host Organisations may wish to compare the information on a User Organisation’s website against their internal set of criteria covering the properties of User Organisations they will in principle share data with for research. For example, checking the User Organisation has the right motivations for accessing research data when using data that may be sensitive or confidential.</p>	
<p>Data security compliance</p>	<p>To assess the User Organisation’s accreditation and/or expertise to work with the data effectively</p>	<p>TREs/SDEs/Safe Havens by their very nature provide enhanced security controls. Users are provided with a remote secure connection to work within these environments i.e. security controls are placed upon Users by the Host Organisation. Therefore, Host Organisations may consider it is not necessary for them to assess the security accreditations of the User Organisation.</p> <p>Some accreditations/certifications provide confidence that a User Organisation do follow some additional controls e.g. Cyber Essentials certification requires staff to be appropriately trained in cyber security. Host Organisations should assess if these additional controls are relevant enough to be assessed.</p> <p>If, for a particular Project, data sets are to be extracted and provided to a User Organisation for analysis within their own computing infrastructures rather than within a Host Organisation managed TRE (e.g. a Project involving consented cohort of data where a TRE environment cannot meet the technical needs of the project) then assessment of a</p>	

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		<p>User Organisations data security accreditations /certifications</p> <p>Accreditations to consider regarding data security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber Essentials • Cyber Essentials+ • ISO27001 • DSPT 	
<p>Confirmation of affiliation for each User</p>	<p>To check that a User Organisation has confirmed the affiliation of a User.</p>	<p>Data Custodians may wish to consider some terms for User Organisations to agree to covering what a User Organisation is confirming when they “confirm User affiliation”. For example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) There is an acknowledged link such a contract of employment, honorary contract or student enrolment between a Users and the Organisation. 2) The Users Organisation approves this employee / student to access sensitive data. 3) The organisational email address of the User corresponds to the correct email address in your Organisation. <p>The individual in the User Organisation who confirmed the User affiliation should be recorded. The Host Organisations may also wish to check that the individual confirming the affiliation of Users holds an appropriate role. For example, it may be appropriate that affiliations are confirmed by a Human Resources representative rather than the Primary Investigator of a Project.</p> <p>Host Organisations may consider agreeing a process for a User Organisation to inform the Host Organisation if a researcher leaves their employment.</p>	<p>A2, A4</p>

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<p>Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)</p>		<p>Host Organisations may wish to capture who in a User Organisation is the Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) for ensuring that the User Organisation comply with their legal responsibilities.</p> <p>Host Organisations may require that SROs are responsible for providing a list of who in their organisation is able to carry out the role of confirming affiliation of Users.</p>	
<p>Organisation Due Diligence Checks</p>	<p>To check that a User Organisation’s morals and values aligns with the Host Organisation’s for the purposes of data access</p>	<p>Host Organisations may wish to consider the ethics of User Organisations who intend to access data for research. For example, a Host Organisation may not wish to share data with insurance companies or with those working in non-ethical domains such as the tobacco industry. They also may have some practical considerations, e.g. checking that the User Organisation has the ability to pay for the costs of the Project.</p> <p>When any organisations assess the properties of another organisation to determine whether it is appropriate to do business together, organisation due diligence checks are often undertaken.</p> <p>Host Organisations should consider which organisational due diligence checks are relevant to their organisation.</p> <p>It may be challenging for a direct employee of the Host Organisation to carry out all of the required due diligence checks. Host Organisations could consider utilising one of the many external companies who collate information from multiple sources and provide a summary due diligence check-list report on organisations.</p>	

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<p>Signed Data Access Agreement</p>		<p>It is recommended a Data Access Agreement is put in place. A Data Access Agreement highlights the responsibilities of the User Organisation and Research Sponsor. It also highlights their responsibilities when Approved Users gain access to data (e.g. responsibility for approved users' compliance with terms of the agreement and ensuring that they are appropriately trained).</p> <p>The Alliance standard Data Access Agreement (DAA) is a template that your organisation can use for the contract between the Research Sponsor and User Organisation(s) for a Project.</p>	
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Projects

The following data should be captured by Host Organisations for each Project.

What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how) (completed where appropriate)	Relevant Best Practice³ (summarised in Appendix A)
Project DUR metadata	It is recommended that the metadata about a Project is captured using the Alliance Data Use Register standard.	<p>The public benefit and lay summary descriptions are often populated by Users within their data access application. This information is then used to populate these sections within a DUR entry.</p> <p>To support Users to draft their lay explanation of a Project the following resources may be helpful:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Research Association - Writing a plain language (lay) summary of your research findings • National Institute for Health Research and Social Care Research - Plain English summaries <p>To support Researchers to ensure the research purpose has a defined public benefit the following resources may be helpful:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The PEDRI standards explain the key factors in effective PPIE • Understanding Patient Data - Data for Public Benefit • Health Research Authority - Impact of public involvement on the ethical aspects of research • National Data Guardian - Public benefit guidance 	Clause 2 of the DAA

³ [Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments](#)

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how) (completed where appropriate)	Relevant Best Practice³ (summarised in Appendix A)
		Host Organisations may wish to share Project metadata on their own webpages and / or existing Data Use registers e.g. Health Data Gateway	
User Organisations	To record which User Organisation legal entities are collaborating on the project and are responsible for the actions of their affiliated Users.	The User Organisations involved in the Project should be recorded and assessed and validated as per the User Organisation section above.	
Users	To record which Users have access to which data for which Project and to understand which User Organisation they are affiliated with for the specific Project	Which User Organisation each User is affiliated with should be recorded. Users should be assessed and validated as per the Users section above. Host Organisation should be able to disbar Users in breach of service, and take appropriate actions with their relevant responsible User Organisation.	
User access to sensitive data	To be able to apply authorisation	Access to sensitive data within a secure environment should be recorded and audited i.e. associate log on accounts with specific validated Users.	A5, A6 Clause 3 of the DAA

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What information is being considered?	Why should this be considered/ collected?	Guidance on factors that impact “safe” status. (how) (completed where appropriate)	Relevant Best Practice³ (summarised in Appendix A)
environments and data	policies to enable access to services based on the access approved for each User		

Appendix A: Summary of Safe People Principles and Good Practices

Good Practice for SAFE People (Analysts): Only trained, authorised individuals can access the data

- A1. Data Custodians should have processes to verify the identity of Individuals from the information they supply
- A2. Data Custodians should have processes to verify the status of Individuals from information they or their Organisations provide regarding their Accredited / Approved / Bonafide analyst / researcher status or equivalent.
- A3. Data Custodians should have processes to verify that Individuals undertake and renew Information Governance Training in support of their accreditation status
- A4. Data Custodians should maintain records of signed agreements by Individuals and Organisations documenting their legal undertakings governing their access to the data, including capturing declarations of funding/sponsorship, commercial interests and any potential conflicts of interest.
- A5. TRE providers should be able to apply authorisation policies to enable access to services based on the access approved for each individual
- A6. TRE providers should maintain a record of all Researcher access performed by Individuals for audit purposes and to generate transparency information on usage.
- A7. Data Custodians should have processes to disbar users in breach of service with an appeals process